

STUDIES ON THE CATAPHORETIC SPEED OF SOL PARTICLES AS DEPENDENT ON THE REDOX POTENTIAL OF THE LIQUID MEDIUM.

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Mobility of colloidal particles of platinum and gold in very dilute aqueous solutions of a few redox systems have been studied. Results indicate that the change in the cataphoretic speed and hence the electrokinetic potential of the gold and platinum particles are not probably due to any specific ion adsorption but are due to more general factors the predominant one being the electron activity of the medium which is responsible for the oxidation-reduction potential of the system.

There are few problems in electrochemistry which are of greater theoretical significance than the absolute single potential of metals but about which there is greater uncertainty.

The Helmholtz-Lippman theory that the surface tension of mercury would increase as the cathode polarisation is increased, and would reach a maximum when the potential between mercury and solution has a zero-value gave in the hands of skilful investigators the value of $E_h = -0.277$ as the zero-point of absolute potential (Kruger and Krummrich, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1913, 19, 667.)

The same value of the zero-point of absolute potential is also obtained by the use of dropping mercury electrode (Palmaer, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 28, 265; 1899, 28, 257; Nernst, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1906, 12, 192).

The reliability of the single electrode potentials derived according to the above two methods was not questioned so long as these were the only two methods available. Doubts were cast on this value of single potential by the investigation of Billiter who by careful sampling, investigated the changes in solution taking place in the vicinity of drop electrodes. Assuming that the observed changes were due to changes in the concentration of Hg^{++} ion, he concluded that the zero point of absolute potential occurs between $E_h = +0.4$ and $E_h = +0.5$ (Billiter, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1904, 48, 513). Similar results have been obtained later by Garrison, Bennowitz and other workers.

According to Freundlich, we must distinguish between (i) the true thermodynamic potential E which is the potential of metal surface against the movable liquid and is due to the reversible transformation :

where (e) is the electron concentration, and (ii) the electrokinetic potential which is the potential between the thin liquid film directly in contact with the solid metal surface and adhering firmly to it and the readily movable liquid. Variation of electrokinetic motion and even its reversal only indicate the corresponding changes in ξ potential and may not throw much light on the absolute value of E , the thermodynamic potential.

This objection has also been raised against "Schabe method" of Bennewitz and it is maintained that scraping with an agate edge cannot remove the firmly adhering liquid film from the metal surface and only the outer surface of the electrical double layer can be scraped away.

By studying the effect of concentrations c of salts on the variation of ξ and E for the same surface, it has been possible to show in some cases the very marked difference in the $\xi-c$ and $E-c$ curves. Taking advantage of the fact that glass acts like a hydrogen electrode over a wide range of p_H , Freundlich *et al* (*Preuss. Akad. Wiss.*, 1920, 20, 397) have made a direct comparison of the effect of salt on E and ξ . It was found that the $\xi-p_H$ and $E-p_H$ curves of a glass surface covered with a thin film of adsorbed serum albumin in acetate buffers of the same ionic strength had *opposite* slopes.

This is an interesting observation, and it was considered desirable to study the ξ potential of noble metals in a liquid environment whose electron activity is known. It is customary now-a-days to describe oxidation-reduction processes in terms of transference of electrons. In a reversible reaction of the type $AH_2 \rightleftharpoons A + 2H^+ + 2e$, the logarithms of the electron activity is given by the equation

$$\log (e) = \frac{1}{2} \log \frac{(AH_2)}{(A)} + \log \frac{1}{H^+} + \text{constant},$$

and the oxidation-reduction potential of a solution containing such a system is a measure of the electron activity and is given by the corresponding equation

$$E_{\text{Redox}} = E_0 - 0.03 \log \frac{(AH_2)}{(A)} - 0.06 p_H \text{ at } 25^\circ.$$

We have in this investigation, studied the mobility of colloidal particles of platinum and gold in very dilute aqueous solutions of the following redox systems :

Lauth's violet (thionine), *o*-bromophenol indophenol, *o*-chloroindo-2 : 6-dichlorophenol, methylene blue, potassium indigo-tetra-sulphonate and *o*-cresol indophenol. These dyes have been specially prepared for oxidation-reduction work in laboratories of the British Drug Houses and were

certified to be pure analytical reagents. The potential at p_H 7 varied from +0.23 volt in the case of bromophenol to -0.046 volt in the case of potassium indigo-tetrasulphonate. The dyes were also selected with a view to obtaining in some cases positive dye ion, and in others, negative dye ion. The velocity of the particles was measured in an electrophoresis cell of cylindrical cross section in conjunction with a Zeiss Ultramicroscope outfit (Mattson, *Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1922, 14, 227; Svedberg and Anderson, *Kolloid Z.*, 1919, 24, 156).

A 500 c.p. Edison point-o-lite lamp was used in place of an electric arc for intense illumination of the ultramicroscopic field, as unlike the ordinary arc it did not require any attention during the experiment.

The electron activity of the solution has been varied by changing the ratio of oxidant to reductant and also by changing p_H by the addition of a few drops of a dilute solution of ammonia and acetic acid as the case may be. Buffer solutions cannot be used as they coagulate the solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The details of experimental arrangement and procedure are given below.

The dye solution (0.005%) was freshly prepared every day. The reduction of the dye has to be effected by reagents which will not increase the ionic strength of the solution, nor should they be so surface active that the colloidal particles get coated with a film of these reagents. After many trials, the following two methods were found suitable :—

(a) Reduction with hydrogen in presence of platinum black which was prepared according to the method of Willstätter and Waldschmidt Leitz (*Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1921, 54, 113) and kept after purification under conductivity water.

(b) Reduction with hydrazine hydrate, always taking care that the dye to be reduced is in excess, so that the hydrazine hydrate added to the solution is completely decomposed. The gaseous decomposition products in this case were removed from the system by streaming with pure nitrogen.

Fig. 1 will make the procedure clear. 0.005% Dye solution was kept in the flask (1) which was gently heated and was reduced by streaming pure H_2 gas in presence of platinum black. The reduced product is very unstable and is easily oxidised by the oxygen of the air. Hence air is completely excluded from the system. The dye was reduced to the extent desired and was then transferred by excess of H_2 pressure to the flask

FIG. 1.

Ultra-microscope Arrangement.

- Pt. electrodes 9 and 10 leading to the H. T. cells, voltage varying between 60 and 220.
 7—Calomel decinormal electrode. The Pt. electrode 8 and 7 are joined to the potentiometer.
 Pt. electrodes 3 and 4 are connected with the conduction apparatus.
 5—Cataphoretic cell.
 6—Microscope.

containing colloidal gold after filtering the dye through a filter paper attached to the tube (b). In order that the reduced dye might not be oxidised by the oxygen of the air contained in the flask (2), H_2 gas was first passed for five minutes in the gold sol, previous to admixture with the dye solution. Then the reduced dye and the gold sol (1 : 1) was mixed thoroughly by bubbling H_2 gas and allowed to attain the temperature of the room.

This process of reducing dye was followed only in the case of gold sol. We have observed that colloidal particles of platinum get coated with a film of hydrogen gas which is not immediately removed by even bubbling nitrogen. The particles showed irregular movement and the velocity in the electrical field could not be measured. In this case the dyes were partly reduced by hydrazine hydrate solution and through the reduced dye N_2 gas was passed in order to avoid oxidation.

The colloidal solutions of gold and platinum were prepared by Bredig's method in conductivity water.

The mixture of the reduced dye and the gold sol was allowed to pass into the cataphoretic cell half an hour after stopping the current

of H_2 or N_2 . Then a high tension field was introduced through a variable resistance to the mixture (dye + sol) by the electrodes 9 and 10. By means of the commutator (C) the current was reversed. The cataphoretic movement was measured in both directions taking five observations in each direction by focussing at a depth of 0.14 diameter of the Mattson cell according to the equation

$$U \left(\frac{2a^2}{r^2} - 1 \right) = 0 \text{ or } a = \frac{r}{\sqrt{2}}$$

where a = distance from the axis or 0.14 of the cell's diameter in the case of Mattson cell.

The time required for a particle to pass through a definite distance of the micrometer scale in the microscope was observed by a stop-watch. The results were checked in typical cases by noting the cataphoretic speeds at different depths when a parabolic curve was obtained.

The particles of gold and platinum were as usual negatively charged.

Specific Conductivity of the Mixture (dye and sol) and the Potential Gradient in the System.—For this two platinum wires (3 and 4) were introduced into one of the side-tubes attached to the cataphoretic cell and the cell constant was determined by measuring the conductivity of a solution of KCl of known strength ($N/50$). The specific conductivity of the dye solutions containing the sol is then determined in each case and knowing the dimensions of the cataphoretic cell, it is possible to calculate the resistance of 1 c.c. of column of the dye solution in the observation cell. The current passing through the high tension circuit was read by the deflection of a calibrated galvanometer. The potential gradient in the cataphoretic cell was thus easily calculated.

E. M. F. Measurement.—The redox potential of the mixture was determined *in situ* by first switching off the high tension circuit and then measuring the potential of the platinum wire (8) against a known electrode $N/10$ -KCl-calomel electrode (7) by a potentiometer.

p_H Measurement.—After the cataphoretic velocity had been determined mixture was taken out from the cataphoretic cell and the p_H of the mixture was measured by a glass electrode. The velocities were also measured at different depths of the cataphoretic cell and they were found to lie on a parabola. After every observation, the cell was cleansed by acid and alkali. The experimental data are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Gold Sol.

Thionine.				Methylene blue.			
Eh.	Reduction.	$p_{H.}$	Vo.	Eh.	Reduction.	$p_{H.}$	Vo.
+0.0556	15%	8.0	21.4×10^{-5}	+0.015	7.0%	8.0	25.7×10^{-5}
+0.009	85.0	,,	25.7	-0.031	71.0	,,	27.8
-0.028	98.5	,,	28.9	-0.048	88.5	,,	31.5
+0.16	27.0	5.0	14.9	-0.063	96.0	,,	33.0
+0.09	99.0	,,	18.7	+0.18	1.0	5.0	13.9
+0.18	16.5	4.7	12.4	+0.136	7.0	,,	16.7
+0.103	11.0	6.8	16.8	+0.105	39.0	,,	17.6
-0.023	58.0	8.4	25.8	+0.32	99.5	,,	20.9
				+0.13	23.0	5.0	14.9
				+0.11	1.0	6.0	14.5

TABLE II.

Platinum Sol.

Thionine.				Methylene blue.			
Eh.	Reduction.	$p_{H.}$	Vo.	Eh.	Reduction.	$p_{H.}$	Vo.
+0.065	9.0%	8.0	17.3×10^{-5}	+0.0214	4.0%	8.0	21.0×10^{-5}
+0.0516	19.0	,,	18.3	-0.023	58.5	,,	23.1
+0.0105	78.0	,,	21.7	-0.052	92.0	,,	24.7
+0.18	30.0	4.5	10.1	+0.14	4.0	5.0	12.4
+0.13	96.8	,,	12.4	+0.101	52.0	,,	13.9
+0.10	94.0	5.0	15.2	+0.103	12.0	5.4	14.5
+0.12	42.0	5.3	12.0	+0.08	24.0	5.6	15.8
				-0.05	33.4	8.2	21.7

DISCUSSION.

Detailed investigations of the electrochemical properties of gold sol have already been carried out by Zsigmondy and co-workers, Pauli and co-workers, and by Beans and Eastlack and co-workers. It has been claimed by the last group of workers that gold sol by Bredig's method can only be prepared if the water contains traces of Cl ion. Pauli and Kautzki did not find any Cl ion, either in the gold gel or the filtrate from such a gel. Pauli maintains that the negative charge of gold sol is due to the surface being coated with $\text{Au}(\text{OH})_4$ ion which is analogous in composition to AuCl_4 ion. In our experiments the colloidal particles of gold were treated with hydrogen gas before being admixed with a redox indicator dye, the reducing potential of both hydrogen and the dye being such as to reduce completely microscopic particles of gold oxide. It is debatable whether in such an environment, the hydroxy gold ion is capable of stable existence.

The influence of OH^- ion on the cataphoretic speed of colloidal gold has been studied by Pauli and Fuels and Thiessen and Henmann. The values change from 30×10^{-5} approximately to 35×10^{-5} , when the final

FIG. 2.

Gold sol.

concentration of K_2CO_3 added is $1 \times 10^{-3}N$. Our experimental results on the relation between the redox potential of the environment and the cataphoretic velocity of gold particles are shown in Fig. 2.

The observations relate to particles of ultramicroscopic sizes, and the redox potential has been varied by (i) choice of suitable indicators, (ii) by changes in the oxidant to reductant ratio, and (iii) by changing p_H by addition of ammonia and acetic acid.

It will be seen that the slope of $E_h - \mu$ (cataphoretic speed) has approximately the same value for all the dye solutions studied. Not only that, the absolute values of μ in different dye solutions, and at different p_H are close to one another, if the redox potential is the same. It is to be noted that some of the dye ions are positively charged and others negatively charged, but their influence on the cataphoretic speed of the negatively charged gold particles is independent of the sign of the charge of the indicator ion, but is dependent on the redox potential of the environment.

The electrochemical properties of platinum sol have been thoroughly studied by Pennyquick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2600; 1928, 551) who postulates the existence of $H_2Pt(OH)_6$. We have observed that unlike the gold sol, hydrogen streamed through a platinum sol changes the surface of the sol particles in such a way that the cataphoretic speed could not be measured with reproducible exactitude. This created the suspicion that the molecules of hydrogen adsorbed by the sol particles adhere tenaciously to the surface and it takes a long time after the bubbling has been stopped before desorption becomes complete. This hypothesis could be tested if a clean platinum wire were dipped into a platinum sol, after it has been streamed with hydrogen, and the potential of the wire against a $N/10$ -calomel electrode measured from time to time.

Time in minutes after stopping the hydrogen stream.	5	30	60	150	180
E_h of the platinum wire in platinum sol.	-0.09	-0.06	+0.34	+0.40	+0.45

It will be seen that the potential of the solution to begin with is negative and not far removed from the potential of the hydrogen electrode. After the 30th minute the adhering film of hydrogen practically disappears and the sol particles cannot function as a reservoir of hydrogen gas. This point is indicated by the sudden jump to high values of positive potential.

In view of this direct evidence of hydrogen film on the surface of colloidal platinum particle, it is worth considering, if the hexahydroxoplatinic acid is not completely reduced in contact with hydrogen.

FIG. 3.
Platinum sol.

The general features of E_h - μ curves in platinum sol (Fig. 3) are similar to those in gold sol.

It will be premature at this stage to try to draw far reaching conclusions from the results recorded here but the inference may easily be made that under the experimental conditions that we have maintained, the change in the cataphoretic speed and hence the electrokinetic potential of the gold and platinum particles are not probably due to any specific ion adsorption but are due to more general factors, the predominating one being the electron activity of the medium, which is responsible for the oxidation-reduction potential of the system. It is also to be noted that if the E_h - μ curves are extrapolated to zero value of μ , they all tend to cut the E_h axis between +0.35 and +0.45 volts. It is significant that these values of electrode potential are in the neighbourhood of those obtained by Billiter and Garrison.

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